

A Study on the Vocabulary of Geography in Relation to Achievement in the Subject at Secondary Level in WB

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ABSTRACT : With a few examples the authors have shown that Bengali Vocabulary of school Geography suffers from ambiguity. They have tried to ascertain the vocabulary of the students of class IX in Geography sex-wise & habitat-wise and have also tried to find the correlation between vocabulary and achievement scores in Geography. Sample for the work was mainly collected from the districts adjoining Kolkata by cluster sampling method. The mean Vocabulary scores of the groups were nearly 50% of the full marks and maximum score was far below the full marks. ANOVA shows that the different groups do not differ significantly in their mean Vocabulary scores. Also Vocabulary and achievement Scores in Geography are positively and significantly correlated. Authors suggest that (i) consensus in Geography vocabulary in Bengali is necessary and (ii) under unavoidable situations, some English vocabulary may be retained.

Keywords : Vocabulary, Achievement.

Introduction

Superseding its history of poor curriculum and weightage, geography was introduced in 1974 in the Secondary Final curriculum with higher weightage i.e. 12% in WB. This curriculum of geography was distributed uniformly over physical geography and regional geography with

bias on environmental education. There after the economic geography found its place in the School geography curriculum.

The teaching learning process in geography could not change at par with the change of geography curriculum. It was maintained at a lower key in different schools as evident from several actions-

- i) It has been taught by the persons not having specialization in geography.
- ii) It was not found in the list of likings of the school students.
- iii) Geography teaching was heavily banked on torn or old maps.
- iv) It was taught mostly in the last period of the school and as such the students could not be motivated towards the subject.

at Secondary and higher Secondary levels in a more dignified way.

As a result of the above changes in geography education, the conceptual structure of geography changed. At present geography has attained a lofty position in school curriculum as a conceptual subject like physics and mathematics.

In spite of the advances in geography mentioned above, geography has to travel a longer path to be taught through regional or mother languages. The vocabulary developed in regional or mother languages are not always unique, distinct or unambiguous. These problems exist more or less in Bengali vocabulary also. So attention must be paid to develop unique vocabulary in Bengali. The lack of unique vocabulary at present in Bengali presents a difficulty of development of concept as the vocabulary act as label to the concepts. If vocabulary remains ambiguous, its effect may be serious on development of concept in Geography. So attention must be paid to develop unique vocabulary in Bengali. An example of ambiguous vocabulary is shown in table-1.

The Scenario began to Change

- a) Geography has been introduced as an elective subject in +2 levels both in rural and urban areas.
- b) The students with specialization and dedication in geography came to teach geography as a teacher in Secondary, Higher Secondary as well as in Degree colleges.
- c) The colleges of rural and urban areas introduced specialization course in geography at general and advance levels.
- d) New geography department were opened under different academic universities.
- e) Scope of employment of geography students in different Govt. and non Govt. organization gradually increased.
- f) There is climax of geography education due to introduction of computer, internet, Google's Earth (Maps) and wall paper.
- g) Field trips and Project works was introduced in geography education both

Geography Vocabulary in Bengali and its Ambiguity

The above Geographical terms (Vocabulary) in Bengali (medium) were collected from several Text Books of School Geography written by noted experts.

From the table, it is understood that there exists unique vocabulary for different geographical objects or phenomenon or process in English. But the same is not applicable in the case of vocabulary in Bengali medium.

Table:1. English vocabulary & corresponding Bengali vocabularies (written in Bengali accent.) as noted in school Geography text books

English Vocabulary	Bengali Equivalents	
	1 st version	2 nd version
Weathering	Abahabiker	Silabiker
Mountain	Pahar	Parbat
Vernal Equinox	Basanta Bisub	Mahabisub
International Date Line	Din paribartaner rekha	Tarikh Bibhajika/Antar jatik Tarikh Rekha
Trade Wind	Banijya Bayu	Ayan Bayu
Westerly Wind	Paschima Bayu	Pratyayan Bayu
Wind	Bayu	Batas
Cataract	Kharasrot	Dhapjukta Gatimay Jalaprapat
Rapid	Kshudra Jalaprapat	Dhapjukta Kshudra Kshudra Jalaprapat

Sometimes different words or set of words exist in Bengali vocabulary corresponding to one and the same English vocabulary. In the table-1, nine terms have been identified whose Bengali equivalents are not unique. In most of the Books one Bengali term has been used in lieu of others used in other text books. These produce an ambiguity during concept formation. For example the difference between hill (Pahad) and mountain (Parbat) are not strictly adhered everywhere. It may so happen that Geography vocabulary in Bengali has been developed late in comparison to English version vocabulary. More vocabulary is yet to be formed or sought after. Students reading one term in a Book cannot understand a question utilizing different term with the same meaning. It may so happen that the students with low performance ability might do better in the Concept Test, if the corresponding vocabulary is known to him /her through class Text Books.

Characteristics of Vocabulary

Vocabulary has essentially the following characteristics:

- a) Insistence on definition: A term may be concrete or abstract, but the definition of the term requires a universal acceptance. Symbols or abbreviation are also used in lieu of words .
- b) Suppression of peripheral meaning: It is divided into two types-
 - i) *Denotative* meaning : Denotative or extensional or referent meaning refers to the literal meaning of a word, the “dictionary definition”.
 - ii) *Connotative* or *associational* meaning: It indicates subsidiary meaning or the associations that are connected to a certain word or the emotional suggestions related to that word. The connotative

meanings of a word exist together with the denotative meanings.

Types of Vocabulary

There are two types of vocabularies – Expressive and Receptive.

This classification owes its credit to Neuman and Dwyer (2009) who divided vocabulary into the above two categories.

Each subject or discipline has its own specialized terminologies which are used in particular content areas. It also plays an important role for understanding the content areas and the academic success depends on it. As Vacca and Vacca (2008), have stated, words are labels for concept and so teaching vocabulary is actually teaching about the ideas they present.

Vocabulary may not always consists of some verbal words. Sometimes, it may also consists of some non-verbal symbols e.g. “drawing of maps and diagrams in geography.” Having knowledge about a subject helps children learn new and related words and learning a new word means developing a concept or ideas related to that word. “A new word is acquired through many encounters with its definition” (Hedrick et al:2004).

Problem

Ku Yu-Mir, 2001 and Alshamrani (2003) studied the means of improvement of vocabulary. Schuster(2000) studied the development of vocabulary among the elementary students. Rath and Nayak (1998), Mukherjee,1997 studied the achievement in Mathematics caste-wise and sex-wise respectively. Vandalen and Mohr, 1981 examined the relation between vocabulary and achievement . Jain, 1995 and De (1991)

examined the relation between vocabulary and achievement in Sanskrit and Physical Science respectively at secondary level. According to Hoff, this finding points to the vital importance of vocabulary because, theoretically, if SES and other SES-related factors measured in those studies were somehow magically fixed, children with larger vocabulary would still perform better in school. A survey of the studies shows that very little work has been done on the vocabulary of Geography. Researches on relation between vocabulary and achievement have been done mostly in primary level. So it is necessary to know, how far the vocabulary helps the achievement in different school subjects particularly Geography, the subject whose Bengali medium vocabulary are of recent origin and are ambiguous in some cases. A study on the vocabulary and achievement seems to be necessary for the students who are pursuing Geography in Bengali medium. The topic for the problem for the study might emerge as “A study on the vocabulary of Geography in relation to Achievement in the Subject at Secondary Level in WB”

Delimitation

That study has the following delimitations.

- i) The population of this study constitutes class –IX students who are just promoted to class –IX.
- ii) The schools taken for the study were Bengali medium school under the jurisdiction of WBBSE.
- iii) The number of schools taken are 16 (Boys school 8 and Girls school 8) and number of subjects (students) taken are 800 (400 Boys and 400Girls).

- iv) The schools selected for the study belong to the districts of Howrah, Hooghly and North 24 Parganas respectively.
- v) Convenient sampling method was used to gather data from the subjects.
- vi) Only the content of physical geography was taken as the content sample.

H₀₂ Students would not differ sex-wise in vocabulary scores in Geography.

H₀₃ Urban Students would not differ sex-wise in vocabulary scores in Geography.

H₀₄ Rural Students would not differ sex-wise in vocabulary scores in Geography.

H₀₅ Girls of different habitats would not differ in vocabulary scores in Geography.

H₀₆ Boys of different habitats would not differ in vocabulary scores in Geography.

H₀₇—Vocabulary scores obtained by the students would not be correlated with Achievement scores in Geography.

Objectives

The objectives of the present study are as follows:

- i) To determine the significance of difference in mean scores habitat-wise in vocabulary test in Geography.
- ii) To determine the significance of difference in mean scores sex-wise in vocabulary test in Geography.
- iii) To determine the inter-relationship between the Achievement Scores in Geography and Vocabulary Scores in Geography.

Methodology

Tools: The researcher has used two tools – A Vocabulary Test and Achievement Test in geography, WBBSE.

a) A Vocabulary Test in Geography (Sarkar and De,2012)

The dimensions of the test are-

- a) Substitution of a group of words by a single word.
- b) Antonyms,
- c) Word Completion,
- d) Word Identification,
- e) Interpretation of symbols,
- f) Labeling of diagrams.

The number of items was 65 .The full marks were 65. Duration of test was 30 m. Its reliability was found by test –retest methods and its face validity was determined by college and school teachers in Geography.

Research Questions

- 1) Do the students of rural and urban background differ in the vocabulary used in school Geography?
- 2) Do the Boys & Girls differ in the vocabulary used in school Geography?
- 3) Is there any correlation between vocabulary and achievement in geography among the school student?

Hypotheses

H₀₁—Students would not differ habitat-wise in vocabulary of Geography

b) Achievement Test in Geography :

Geography Tests in Secondary Examination of West Bengal Board of Secondary Education was considered as Achievement Test in Geography. The items corresponding to class IX syllabus were collected by the present investigators from the Geography question papers set during 2009 -12 for the Secondary Final Examination under West Bengal Board of Secondary Education. As the questions were set in the Final Examination, its standardization was not necessary. It consists of short answer and very short answer type questions covering the erstwhile syllabus of class IX. The full marks of the test were 20 and number of items was 10 (S.A-5 and V.S.A-5)

Sample

The sample of the study consists of 800 students (400 Boys and 400 girls) of class IX just promoted to class-X were taken from both rural-urban areas from Secondary (8Boys &8 Girls) Schools under WBBSE. The schools were located in three districts of W.B. i.e. Howrah, Hooghly and North 24 Parganas.

The convenient sampling technique was used for the purpose. The number and categories of the students are shown below:

SEX↓ HABITAT→	Urban	Rural	Total
Boys	200	200	400
Girls	200	200	400
Total	400	400	800

TABLE-2. Frequency Distribution of the Vocabulary Scores in Geography(Full marks-57)

Vocabulary Scores	10.00-14.00	15.00-19.00	20.00-24.00	25.00-29.00	30.00-34.00	35.00-39.00	40.00-44.00	Total
Frequency	33	43	84	177	232	190	41	800

Presentation of the Scores

To understand the basic nature of distribution of vocabulary scores in geography irrespective of sex and habitat of the students, the frequency distribution of total sample is shown in table-2. Table -3 shows all frequency distribution of vocabulary scores are negatively skewed. It also shows descriptive statistics of the vocabulary scores and the frequency distribution of achievement scores in geography.

Analysis of the Result

To identify the significant difference, if any, among the different groups of students by ANOVA, 30 students were randomly selected from each of the stated groups. Here total sample acts as a sample frame. Descriptive statistics of each group of students have been shown in table-5.

Findings

- 1) From Table 6, it is observed that F- ratio is not significant for sexes, habitat and also for interaction. This indicates that the difference of mean scores is not significant sex-wise, habitat-wise and also for interaction. Hence, null hypotheses from H_{01} to H_{06} are retained. And it is concluded that the groups do not differ on mean vocabulary scores.
- 2) Table-7. shows that correlation between vocabulary scores and achievement

TABLE-3 . Descriptive Statistics for Vocabulary Scores

	Vocabulary Scores								
	Boys	Girls	Total Students Scores of Boys & Girls	Urban	Rural	Urban Boys	Urban Girls	Rural Boys	Rural Girls
Number	400	400	800	400	400	200	200	200	200
Mean	30.157	29.672	29.915	29.94	29.89	29.3	30.58	31.015	28.765
SD	7.519	6.523	7.038	6.322	7.697	7.174	5.277	7.773	7.471
Median	31	30	31	30	31	30	30	32	30
Q1	26	26	26	27	25.75	25	27.75	27	24
Q3	37	35	35	34	36	34	34	37.25	35
Q	5.5	4.5	4.5	3.5	5.12	4.5	3.63	5.13	5.5
Sk	-0.591	-0.708	-0.625	-0.61	-0.619	-0.579	-0.349	-0.674	-0.642
Ku	-0.399	0.541	-0.091	0.354	-0.443	-0.236	0.714	-0.448	-0.395

TABLE-4. Frequency Distribution of Achievement Scores In Geography (Full marks-20)

Ach. Scores	3.00-5.00	6.00-8.00	9.00-11.00	12.00-14.00	15.00-17.00	18.00-20.00	Total
Frequency	2	21	106	258	243	170	800

TABLE-5. Statistical Measures for randomly selected 30 students from different groups in the Vocabulary Test in Geography

Groups	N	Vocabulary Scores	
		Mean	SD
Urban Boys	30	29.433	7.214
Urban Girls	30	30.433	4.553
Rural Boys	30	30.333	8.091
Rural Girls	30	28.833	8.099
Boys	60	29.883	7.614
Girls	60	29.633	6.564
Urban	60	29.933	6.002
Rural	60	29.583	8.062

scores is significant, high and positive. So, the null hypothesis H_{07} is rejected. This shows that vocabulary is highly correlated with achievement.

Results

1. The students studying geography at school level do not differ on vocabulary scores sex-wise, habitat-wise and also interaction-wise (habitat x sex)
2. Vocabulary scores and the achievement scores are significantly and positively correlated in Geography

Discussion

- The students do not differ on vocabulary scores but it is to be seen that the

TABLE-6. Sex-wise and habitat-wise F-ratio for the significance of difference among different groups in Vocabulary Test in Geography

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
hbt	3.675	1	3.675	.072	.789
sex	1.875	1	1.875	.037	.848
hbt * sex	46.875	1	46.875	.920	.340
Error	5911.567	116	50.962		
Total	5963.992	119			

TABLE-7. Bivariate Coefficient of Correlation between Vocabulary and Achievement Scores in Geography

Scores Considered in		df	Coefficient of correlation	Significance
Vocabulary Test 800	Achievement Test 800	798	0.678	P<0.01

students, at best, have not scored 75% of the full marks in vocabulary test. 25 % vocabulary is yet to be mastered by the students. Students could not touch the maximum scores probably due to the ambiguous position of some geography vocabulary (in Bengali Medium).

- The districts chosen were very nearer to Kolkata. The students of these places possess diverse formal and informal vocabularies. As such, the difference in vocabulary scores among them might be negligible. To increase the vocabulary of the students in Geography, unique Bengali vocabulary in Geography is to be developed among them. Signs and symbols as vocabulary may also be developed so that such vocabularies are independent of any language.

- When Bengali vocabulary is fragile, English vocabulary may be introduced.
- A survey may be conducted to find the acceptability of different geographical vocabulary among the students and their geography teachers following the techniques of Biswas (2012).

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